

LINGUISTICS AND PSYCHOLINGUISTICS FOR CRISIS MANAGEMENT AND CRISIS COMPUTING - 3 RESEARCH PROJECTS HIGHLIGHTS

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Abstract

This article represents the contents of an invited talk at the 1st edition of “The International Symposium of Disaster & Emergency – Information & Intervention: Information Management and Response in Disaster and Emergencies” (SODEII 2022). The article presents the applications of Linguistics and Psycholinguistics to the fields of Crisis Management and Crisis Computing. The applications of Linguistics and Psycholinguistics are discussed because they are the scientific areas, which focus on the way in which humans communicate and understand each other. In this way, the methods from these two areas are used to contribute to two important aspects of Crisis Management - specifically Information Management and Communication Strategies. They do this *not* in terms of the selection or the contents of the information to be delivered to the public, but rather regarding how to *best transmit the desired message and meaning*. The paper illustrates their application to the fields of Crisis Management and Crisis Computing, by providing a summary of three completed research projects, which use a mixture of methods from all these fields. All three projects consist in highly interdisciplinary scientific research, practically applied to reality. Two of the three projects concern evaluating and improving the comprehensibility (understandability) of texts, delivered by official authorities to the general public in crisis or disaster situations. The third research project presents a different application - a linguistic resource, aiming to assist with the recognition and extraction of relevant disaster social media messages for Crisis Management and Crisis Computing purposes, which is achieved by applying linguistic and Natural Language Processing methods.

Keywords:

Linguistics, Psycholinguistics, Crisis Management, Crisis Computing, Natural Language Processing

1. Introduction and Aim

This article addresses the use of methods from the Linguistics and Psycholinguistics fields for more efficient communication between authorities and the general public and for relevant crisis and disaster information discovery in the ocean of social media posts.

Linguistics is defined as the scientific study of *language*, both written and oral, addressing all its existing rules of forming words and structures, including phonetics, word morphology, grammatical structures, meaning and semantics, and the historical development of language, for all languages in the world [1, 2, 3].

Psycholinguistics or the *Psychology of Language* is considered to be both a subfield of Linguistics and an interdisciplinary area between Linguistics and Psychology. It studies the way in which people learn, produce, and understand language [1].

It is known that the primary function of language is communication [1] and it is a form of joint action, where people collaborate to achieve a common aim [1]. Efficient communication is crucial in crisis and disaster situations, and thus it is important to use knowledge and methods from the Linguistic and Psycholinguistic fields in the Crisis and Disaster management domains as both these areas study the way in which humans communicate and understand each other. Linguistic and psycholinguistic knowledge is also important for Crisis Computing (also known as 'Disaster Informatics') because it is a source of very useful and widely-used language-centered features for automatic tasks (e.g. for Machine Learning).

There are various applications of Linguistics and Psycholinguistics to both the Crisis Management and Crisis Computing fields. Some examples include: suicide prevention (by manually or automatically recognizing early language signs of potential suicide); both manual and automatic monitoring of citizens communications in social media during crisis events to collect information for situational awareness [4, 5]; analysing the appropriateness of communications of authorities to the general public [6]; defining general and specialized crisis glossaries [7]; studying language behaviour and style as a measure of urgency in crisis messages in social media [8]; and researching how second-language speakers understand emergency communications [9].

This article presents the results achieved during three applied and interdisciplinary research projects. Due to space limitations, the article shows only their highlights. The first two projects (Section 2 and Section 3) address the evaluation and improvement of understandability of two different types of written texts, communicated by various types of authorities to the general public during crisis situations. Understandability (also called *comprehensibility* or *readability*) is addressed from the point of view of Psycholinguistics - specifically, which types of words and syntactic structures are harder or easier to understand.

The third project (Section 4) exemplifies the use of Linguistics in Crisis Computing, by presenting the methods and results of collecting a large number of relevant keywords (linguistic expressions), which allow to recognize and extract (both manually and automatically) social media posts, highly relevant to different aspects of disasters. Extracting such posts can be used further to build disaster-specific situational awareness from crisis tweets.

2. Project 1: Understandability of Emergency Instructions

The first project addresses the comprehensibility of emergency instructions and proposes detailed guidelines on how to write such instructions in a clear and understandable way. The research has been done as part of the MESSAGE project¹, a project, funded under the “Prevention, Preparedness and Consequence Management of Terrorism and other Security-related Risks” Programme of the European Commission - Directorate-General Justice, Freedom and Security. The project consisted in linguistic and psycholinguistic research of the understandability and on methods to write clear to understand emergency instructions and messages from the authorities to the general public in several European languages - French, English, Spanish, Polish, and Bulgarian. The current article describes the research done for English and its evaluation results.

2.1. Materials and Methods

This project applies *methods from Psycholinguistics*, and specifically the knowledge that natural language can often be complex and contain ambiguities [1]. Complexity and ambiguity can appear at different levels - including as words or syntactic structures and syntactic agreement. While different languages can be characterised with different language-specific complexity and ambiguity phenomena, there are some general phenomena, applicable to several languages (for example the long and complex sentences and words with several frequent meanings are comprehensibility issues in several European languages). Another problem is that while some readers should understand even more complex and ambiguous texts, there are readers, who may have lower cognitive skills due to a specific temporal or permanent cognitive condition, lower literacy, or simply be foreigners, who do not know the current country environment and the commonly accepted names.

The project addresses these issues by using a solution called “*controlled language*”. A controlled language is an artificially constructed subset of the natural language, which has been limited in terms of the allowed words, their allowed meanings, and the permitted to be used syntactic structures, in order to avoid or reduce ambiguity and complexity [10]. Controlled languages are widely used in technical manuals, while those of them which address human comprehension are based on psycholinguistic rules, such as:

- Write short sentences.
- Avoid negation.
- Use simple words.
- Write instructions in a logical order.

The research was done using a variety of written emergency instructions in American and British English, which have been retrieved from the Web (in 2010-2011) from official sources (including the United States Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), and the British Red Cross) and in consultation with the Resilience Unit of the UK’s Sandwell Council. The project focussed on emergency instructions for the general public (in total 150 000 words), which were a subset of a larger

¹ <http://message-project.univ-fcomte.fr/>. Last accessed on February 11, 2022.

collection (over 2 700 000 words) of crisis management instructions and alerts (mostly collected from the web), named the Crisis Management Corpus (CMC) [11].

The project produced the Controlled Language for Crisis Management (CLCM) [11], defined in 40 pages guidelines for writing clear emergency instructions in English, with examples, logical and syntactic rules, and a prototype domain dictionary.

Figure 1 shows two CLCM rules. As it can be seen, the rules have a reference number (e.g., “In_L_06”), where “In” stands for “instructions”, “L” for “lexical rule”, and “S” for “syntactic rule”. The rules themselves are also written in accordance with what is allowed or suggested as best practices in the CLCM guidelines. In Rule In_S_06 it is suggested to use “active voice”, as “passive voice” is considered to be hard to understand from the psycholinguistic point of view.

In_L_06: If possible:

Avoid acronyms and abbreviations.

If not:

Use only the acronyms and abbreviations pre-defined in the dictionary.

Contact the NPFS.	Contact the NPFS (National Pandemic Flu Service).
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Explanation: Abbreviations can be ambiguous or unknown to non-native speakers.

In_S_06: Avoid passive voice.

Make sure 999 is called.	Call 999.
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Figure 1: Two CLCM rules.

Figure 2 shows instructions, written according to the CLCM rules (A), and their original version (B).

A:	B:
<p style="background-color: #4a4a9a; color: white; padding: 2px 5px; margin: 0;">How to protect yourself after a volcanic eruption:</p> <p style="background-color: #d1c4e9; padding: 2px 5px; margin: 0;">Turn off:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • heating, • air conditioning units, • fans. <p style="background-color: #d1c4e9; padding: 2px 5px; margin: 0;">Close:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • windows, • doors, • fireplace, • woodstove dampers. <p>• Explanation: This helps keep ash and gases from getting into your house. Exposure to ash can harm your health, particularly the respiratory (breathing) tract.</p>	<p>You can do many things to protect yourself and your family after a volcanic eruption: ... Turn off all heating and air conditioning units and fans, and close windows, doors, and fireplace and woodstove dampers to help keep ash and gases from getting into your house. Exposure to ash can harm your health, particularly the respiratory (breathing) tract.</p>

Figure 2: Instruction, written according to CLCM.

As it can be seen, the rewritten version (A) provides clear division into visible sections, with instructions ordered in a logical way, and separates the actual instructions from the *Explanation*, which is not so urgent to read.

2.2. Findings and Discussion

Several aspects of instructions, written according to the CLCM rules have been evaluated, by running the following experiments:

- 100 participants with different backgrounds and a large variety of Indo-European and non-Indo-European native languages have been asked to answer questions about the original and re-written texts under limited time.
- Professional translators have been asked to:
 - manually translate both original and rewritten texts from English into several European languages (Russian, Bulgarian, Slovenian, Spanish, Greek, Dutch, Maltese).
 - manually correct (so-called “post-edit”) the original and rewritten texts, automatically translated by Google Translate from English into the same languages.

The experiments were designed in such a way that the participants and the translators have *never* seen the same text in both its original and re-written versions.

The results show [11] that the participants gave faster and more correct answers to most of the instructions, which were written according to the CLCM guidelines. An interesting finding (in Figure 3) was discovered when comparing the behaviour of male versus female participants, which were roughly 50-50%. While male participants (with different native languages and backgrounds) gave correct answers to CLCM-rewritten instructions faster, this did not appear to be true for the female participants. More research is necessary to understand the reason.

Figure 3: Time to correctly answer questions for Male and Female participants. “Complex texts” are the original versions, and “simplified texts” - are the CLCM versions.

The manual translation of CLCM instructions was faster for some languages (Bulgarian, Slovenian, Spanish, Maltese), and the machine translation errors were easier and faster to manually correct for all language pairs.

3. Project 2: Understandability of Social Media Posts

The second project [15] analyses and evaluates the understandability of English-language social media posts, published for the general public by governments, media, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) during different types of disasters. The research has been done by part of the Crisis Computing team at the Qatar Computing Research Institute (QCRI). The project also provides simple suggestions for the authorities on how to write clear to understand social media posts for the general public.

3.1. Materials and Methods

This project also uses *the psycholinguistic notions* of which words, expressions, and syntactic structures are easier to understand, and which not. However, the type of texts is different.

This study uses 500 randomly selected *informative* tweets from the CrisisLexT26 [12] collection. The CrisisLexT26 collection contains Twitter messages from 26 different disasters, which occurred worldwide in 2012 and 2013. Each tweet in the collection is annotated for whether it contains useful information that helps to understand the situation (“*informative*” or “*non-informative*”), for type of content (“*affected individuals*”, “*infrastructure and utilities*”,

“*caution and advice*”, etc.), and for source (e.g., *eyewitnesses* and *NGOs*). The tweets used in this study were posted by *NGOs*, *media*, and *governments* during different types of disasters, in different countries (e.g., the floods in Alberta in 2013, bushfires in Australia in 2013, the Boston bombings in 2013, the Singapore haze in 2013, the typhoon Yolanda in the Philippines). Each tweet was further shown to 5 CrowdFlower² workers, who were asked to label it as “*Very clear*”, “*Needs slight improvement*”, and “*Very unclear*”, and in the case in which it was labeled with the last two categories - to provide suggestions about how to rewrite it, in order to make it more understandable.

3.2. Findings and Discussion

The analysis has shown that the 500 crisis tweets posted by NGOs, media, and governments had several comprehensibility issues, some of which were generally psycholinguistic, and some were Twitter-specific (Table 1).

Psycholinguistic	Twitter-specific
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use of acronyms and abbreviations ● Use of unfamiliar words ● Use of long sentences ● Use of impersonal style <p>Ex.: “Police calling for immediate evacuation!” vs. “Evacuate immediately!”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Excessive use of hashtags ● Text choppiness ● Presence of misspellings

Table 1: Comprehensibility issues in the crisis tweets.

These findings confirmed what was observed by others - that often the language used by authorities does not match the knowledge of the general public [6]. The text choppiness and misspellings are typical for the way common users often write their social media posts, which are known to be often ungrammatical and not so fluent. However, this was a surprise for posts, written by official channels.

Table 2 shows other clarity (understandability) results, mostly related to Twitter-specific elements. These results are significant at 0.01 (***) and 0.05 (**) p-values.

² CrowdFlower was the previous name of a large-scale data annotation platform for hiring contractors from over 100 countries. It is currently owned by Appen (<https://appen.com/figure-eight-is-now-appen/> - last accessed on 14 February 2022).

Linguistic characteristics	Very Clear	Needs slight improvement and Very unclear
Average post length (in characters)***	108.6	93.1
Average number of acronyms***	0.3	0.7
Fraction with acronyms***	25.5%	64.8%
Fraction with mentions**	23.5%	38.9%
Fraction with URLs***	56.3%	22.2%
Fraction with hashtags (#)***	68.8%	87.0%
Fraction with hashtags at the beginning***	6.1%	37.0%

Table 2: Numerical amounts of specific characteristics.

Table 2 shows that among the most serious issues, which characterise the two categories of Unclear tweets, are the presence of acronyms in the tweet and hashtags, placed at the beginning of the tweet.

Table 3 shows the number of tweets in each clarity level (“*Very clear*”, “*Needs slight improvement*”, and “*Very unclear*”), and Figure 4 provides examples of “*Very clear*” and “*Very unclear*” tweets.

Clarity of tweets	Percentage
Very Clear	82.1%
Needs slight Improvement	12.0%
Very Unclear	6.0%

Table 3: Percentage of tweets per category of clarity.

Event, year	Source	CrisisLex26 category	Tweet	Clarity
Colorado floods in the USA, 2013	Gover.	Infrastr. and utilities	Colorado flooding doesn't stop Postal Service http://t.co/na58Mmy3an	Very Clear
Typhoon Pablo in the Philippines, 2012	Gover.	Caution and advice	NDRRMC Update SitRep No. 26 re Effects of Typhoon PABLO (BOPHA) as of 13 December 2012. 10:00AM. http://t.co/G8MHAWrq	Very Unclear

Figure 4: Examples of Very clear and Very Unclear tweets.

As a last result, this research produced a small set of suggestions on how to write clear tweets, which can be used to train experts, responsible for writing such messages. The suggestions

address three aspects of the tweets' comprehensibility: message length, vocabulary, and use of Twitter-specific elements, and are listed in Table 4.

Tweets aspect	Suggestions
Message length	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Include a maximum of 1 or 2 main points per tweet. ● Write brief, concise sentences. ● Remove superfluous words. ● Write fully-formed sentences; avoid writing incomplete thoughts, or incomplete messages.
Vocabulary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use only simple and familiar words. ● Use abbreviations and acronyms with care, i.e. only if they are more understandable to the public than their expanded form.
Twitter-specific elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Write a maximum of 2 hashtags. ● Place all hashtags at the end of the tweet; ● Avoid mentions (e.g., "@user").

Table 4: Writing suggestions for clear tweets.

The suggestions in Table 4 can be applied to various languages.

4. Project 3: Large keywords collection for extracting relevant disaster tweets

The third and final project [16] which is presented in this article, concerns a different application - a large comprehensive collection of over 7200 English keywords, reflecting the actual language used in Twitter (in 2015). The collection of keywords (called "terms") can be used to narrow down the manual and automatic search for relevant social media posts and to improve extraction of messages of interest to different disaster management's information needs.

The keywords are divided into categories (rather than into different types of disaster), similar to the categories used in Project 2 - i.e., in terms of what information contents the required social media messages should have (provide information about the weather, disaster victims, shortage of goods and supplies, etc.). While it is very well known that every new disaster is different from the previous ones, the keywords can assist with the search for information present in different types of disasters.

The collection of terms is called "EMTerms 1.0: A terminological resource for crisis tweets" and it is publicly available for download³.

³ <https://crisislex.org/crisis-lexicon.html>. EMTerms 1.0 (paper and resource). Last accessed on 11 February 2022.

4.1. Materials and Methods

Differently from the previous two projects, EMTerms 1.0 has been collected by applying only *linguistic and Natural Language Processing (machine learning) methods*. No Psycholinguistics has been used.

The terms were collected from the tweets from a large collection of 35 disaster events, including all the 26 events in CrisisLexT26 [12] (a subset of which were used in Project 2), however with no restriction on the type of source.

The methods for collecting the terms included several manual and automatic steps. The steps reflected the intuition that the terms used in Twitter by the general public would differ from the specialised disaster glossaries, and thus a look at the Twitter contents discussing real disasters can point to the actual terms used when a disaster occurs.

The first step was to use a small seed set of keywords, manually collected by a crisis manager [14] from tweets discussing 4 events. These keywords were manually labeled by type of content category. After that, a machine learning algorithm (Conditional Random Fields, CRF) was run on all the tweets from the 35 different disasters to collect terms, similar to those in the seed set. The results of this process were a list of terms, each marked with a content category, and accompanied by an example tweet, illustrating the use of the concrete term in a real context.

Two rounds of manual review and filtering of the collected terms, the categories assigned to them, and the associated example tweets followed, one done by a linguist and one by 3 CrowdFlower workers for each term.

The categories used in this project were a modified and expanded version of the categories, used in CrisisLexT26, by making them much more detailed. The categories were coming from 3 different sources: 1) 11 categories from the AIDR classifiers [13], based on the CrisisLex26T categories; 8 categories from the United Nations Humanitarian Cluster System; and 4 new categories, proposed by the authors. The complete list of categories can be found in the related publication [16].

4.2. Findings and Discussion

The collected resource has been presented at the International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM'15) and was encountered with active interest. The resource can be used to simplify manual and to focus automatic extraction of social media posts, relevant to specific disaster management categories. The terms can be used manually in the Twitter search field, or by using specialised platforms, which allow entering a list of keywords and then automatically extracting a large set of tweets, containing these keywords (such as the Artificial Intelligence for Disaster Response (AIDR⁴)), or as features for machine learning algorithms [17].

Figure 5 shows examples of terms with their associated category and an example tweet.

⁴ <http://aidr.qcri.org/>. Last accessed on February 14, 2022.

Term	Category	Example tweet
{Number} flee wildfire	Animal management. Pets and animals, living, missing, displaced, or injured/dead.	32,000 flee wildfire in Colorado. http://t.co/B9kWeVay
extreme rainfall	Weather conditions	Flooding from extreme rainfall is a hazard for ON too. Emergency in #Alberta should be a call to get a 72 hour kit. Better to be prepared.
{Number} critical	Injured people	#LAXShooting @CNN reporting 3 victims at Ronald Reagan UCLA Medical Center, 1 critical
army deployed	Response agencies present at the crisis location	#Pakistan Army deployed for #earthquake rescue operations
{Number} homes destroyed	Need of shelters, including location and conditions of shelters and camps	So sad! 43,000 acres, 5% contained, 500 firefighters... 100 homes destroyed, 1 dead. #wildfire #HighParkFire http://t.co/fpyUydUg
missing	Missing, found, or trapped people	RT @nytimes: Floods Kill 23 in Northern India; Dozens Missing http://t.co/E7DuR61QJY

Figure 5: EMTerms 1.0 examples.

As it can be seen, these terms can be used to collect information about specific aspects of a disaster, such as the disaster victims or the number of affected people. Some of the terms contain a placeholder for “number”, which should be removed if a manual search in the Twitter Search field is performed.

More examples of terms, their category, and illustrative examples of real tweets can be found in the actual terminological resource⁵.

5. Conclusion

This article has presented the contents of an invited talk at The International Symposium of Disaster & Emergency – Information & Intervention: Information Management and Response in Disaster and Emergencies” (SODEII 2022⁶), by showing the applications of Linguistics and Psycholinguistics to three applied research projects. Two of the projects addressed the understandability of crisis and disaster texts, published by authorities for the general public, while the third one presented a large collection of keywords, which can be used to manually or automatically retrieve social media posts, relevant to specific content categories and information needs. The purpose was to illustrate the importance of Linguistics and Psycholinguistics for the Crisis Management and Crisis Computing domains and to inspire the readers to use the results and resources from these three projects or to develop similar ones for their languages and use cases.

⁵ <https://crisislex.org/emterms/EMTerms-v1.0.zip> Last accessed on February 14, 2022.

⁶ <https://sodeii2022.atauni.edu.tr/>. Last accessed on February 13, 2022.

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